

TRADE PERFORMANCE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of international trade on the economic growth in Nigeria (1986-2024). The specific objectives are to; ascertain the effect of balance of payments on the gross domestic product of Nigeria and determine the effect of imports on the gross domestic product of Nigeria. Ex-post facto design was adopted for this study. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was used in testing the two hypotheses formulated. Decisions were based on a 5% level of significance. Results showed that balance of payment has negative but no significant effect on Nigeria's Gross domestic product of Nigeria and import trade has negative but no significant effect on Nigeria's Gross domestic product of Nigeria. Based on findings, it was recommended that manufacturing industries should improve on their production so that their output would be competitive in the global market. Excise duties should be lowered so as to encourage local industries so as to draw foreign investors to Nigeria. It is necessary that conscious efforts should be made by government to fine-tune the various macroeconomic variables in order to provide an enabling environment to stimulate foreign trade by engaging in more in production so as to reduce importation.

Keywords: International Trade; Economic Growth; Gross Domestic Product (GDP); Balance of Payments; Import Trade

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, international trade which involves imports, exports and the balance of payments has reflected contribution towards the direction in which economic growth takes in most countries in the world. Its role is very important and central in the development process of a contemporary global economy. Its impact on the growth and development of countries has increased significantly over the years and has contributed significantly to the progress of the world economy (Ogbaji and Ebebe 2013).

International trade has been an area of interest to policy makers and economists. The importance of international trade lies in the ability to obtain goods which cannot be locally produced in the country or which can only be produced at a greater expense. It also enables a nation to sell its

domestically produced goods to other countries of the world. However, the performance of an economy in terms of growth rates of output has not only been based on the domestic production and consumption activities but also on international transportation of goods and services. The classical

and neo-classical economists attached so much importance to international trade in a country's development in that they regarded it as an engine of growth (Jhingan, 2006).

It is necessary to note that trade globally is recognized as an important catalyst for economic growth and development. For a developing country like Nigeria, the contribution of trade to her overall economic growth is immensely enormous owing largely to the obvious fact that most of the essential elements for development such as raw materials, capital goods and technical know-how, are mostly imported because of inadequate domestic supply.

However, it is very necessary to note that internal trade complements external trade, since domestically produced goods are collected for export whereas imported goods are distributed within the country, sometimes into interior areas of the country. Ngige (2018) inferred that the higher the level of internal trade the greater the level of specialization which raised the level of efficiency and productivity of the people in their various economic units, which enhance rapid economic growth.

Nigeria's economic growth is measured by the gross domestic product (GDP). Therefore, GDP is perceived as a sum total of the market value of a country's output of goods and services, which are exchanged for money or trade in a market system over certain period. This indicates that trade is an important aspect of economic growth. It was observed that the gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria is \$186 billion in 2017. This indicates that the economy has over dependence on the capital-intensive oil sector, which provides 45 per cent of GDP, 95 per cent of foreign exchange earnings and about 65 percent of government revenue for 2020.

International trade has been in existence for centuries and, over time, from the colonization of inhabited and habited parts of the world to the arrival of nations, from mastery to independent countries, from sailboats and caravans to steamboats, cargo planes and truck fleets (Ervok and Oyovvi 2012). There is a need to study its importance on the economy, in other words, from the trade of certain commodities to global production and distribution networks and to the current explosion of international flows of services, capital and information.

Statement of the Problem

One of the serious issues that has obstructed the accomplishment of increase in financial development in Nigeria have been credited to external aggregates such as; Balance of payments constrained growth, exchange rate instability, poor export and dependency on importation (Obayori, 2016) and this has caused economic instability in the country.

An examination of Nigeria's trade profile showed that imbalances persisted in the country's economy since the 80's. The continual imbalances in the Nigerian economy seemingly suggested that government needed to do more to stimulate economic growth and development. Massive oil exportation, Balance of payments constrained growth and the importation of most commodities shows that the country is still under developed, as evidenced by the negative growth rate experienced from first quarter of 2016 to first quarter of 2021.

Thus, the much-awaited impact from international trade in terms of nets import, balance of trade and export trade on Nigerian economy is yet to be felt. It is based on the above state of affairs that this study tends to determine the effect of international trade on economic growth in Nigeria. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of international trade on the economic growth in Nigeria (1986-2024). The specific objectives are to; ascertain the effect of balance of payments on the

gross domestic product of Nigeria and determine the effect of imports on the gross domestic product of Nigeria.

The study focused on the effect of international trade on the economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1986-2024. International trade was proxied by balance of payments, imports and exports while economic growth was proxied by Gross Domestic product (GDP). In justification for the choice of the base year, it is worthy to note that the liberalization (trade liberalization) of the Nigeria economy started in 1986, the upper limit of the time frame (2024) was fixed owing to the availability of relevant dataset.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

International Trade

Bakari (2017) defines international trade as the balance of payments (BOP), exchange of capital, goods, and services across international borders or territories. In most countries, such trade represents a significant share of gross domestic product (GDP).

Terms of Trade: Terms of trade refer to the proportion of exports of goods to the imports of goods in a country. It measures the purchasing power of the country's exports in terms of its imports, hence expressed as a relation between the prices of exports and the prices of imports of goods. Then, when prices of exports increase relative to that of imports the terms of trade are considered to have improved because the country can have a larger quantity of imports compared to exports. Oppositely, the prices of imports increase relative to that of exports, the terms of trade of a country tend to have deteriorated because the country can have smaller import quantities as compared to exports (Krugman et al., 2018).

Balance of Payment: The balance of payment of a country refers to all economic transactions with the outside world recorded systematically in a given particular year. In other words, the balance of payment refers to a way of listing receipts from exports and payments on imports in international transactions of a country, thus it can be used statistically to frame the economic relationships of a country with the outside world. It shows the changes in the country's official reserve holding, the trading position of a country, and the country's net position (foreign lender or borrower) (Krugman et al., 2018).

Export: Export trade is an integral part of international trade, which has to do with selling of goods and services to other countries. International trade depends on some factors referred to as endowment factors which determine the flows of trade among countries. Agu, Amuka & Ugwu (2016) defines export trade as a good or service sold by residents of one country to residents of another in return, usually for foreign exchange. A financial sector in the Heckscher Ohlin trade model showed that financial sector development in general and banking sector in particular gives countries a comparative advantage in industries that rely on external financing. Countries with better developed financial institutions such as banks and markets should therefore, have a comparative advantage in industries that rely relatively more on external finance (Cevis and Camurdan, 2017).

Import: Import trade involves buying of goods and services to other countries. International trade depends on some factors referred to as endowment factors which determine the flows of trade among countries (Cevis and Camurdan, 2017). This is the total number of goods and services purchased by residents of a country, but produced by foreign countries, is a withdrawal from the Tanzanian

economy; hence it is anticipated to be negative. Thus, it is expected that as import value increases GDP will decrease (Krugman et al., 2018).

Economic growth: Economic growth is usually measured with gross domestic product (GDP). Gross domestic product (GDP) is the monetary value of goods and services produced in a nation during a particular period by the residents of that nation irrespective of the nationality of the residents. Economic growth refers to the increase in the inflation-adjusted market value of all goods and services produced by the country's economy over time (Blanchard, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

Neoclassical growth theory

The study adopted the neoclassical growth theory which was developed by Robert Solow(1848). The theory postulates that output is a function of labour and capital. The production function is expressed as: $Y=FR(L, K)$ where Y represent output, k is stock of capital and L is labour. This model is relevant in analyzing globalization, international trade and economic growth because the movement of capital and labour forms the basis for globalization and international trade. The relevance of globalization is determined by the changes in total factor productivity in terms of labour, capital and technological progress (Ogunyomi, Jenrola and Daisi, 2013) in economic growth between the developed and developing nations through technology which is exogenously determined. This divergence in the benefit from globalization also has been linked to the neglect of the manufacturing sector in developing countries including Nigeria which has become retrogressive due to obsolete technology.

The Neo-classical theory of trade evolved in an attempt to modify some unsatisfactory aspects of the classical theory. Thus, the Neo-classical theory, also called the modern theory, advanced a more satisfactory explanation for the existence of comparative cost differences between countries; introduced capital as a second factor of production; and allowed for international differences in the pattern of demand. The Neo-classical theory is therefore a model (i.e., it assumes the existence of two countries, two commodities, and two factors of production). The introduction of a second factor of production turns out to be very important. This makes the approach of Neo-classical theory to be different in certain fundamental respects from the classical theory, namely, in handling of the relationship between factor allocation, income distribution and international trade(Ogunyomi, Jenrola and Daisi, 2013).

Empirical Review

Ibrahim, and Shaibuu (2024) study found significant total impacts (151.585 to 190.139 million Ghana Cedis) in 2017 and 2018, centred around export commodities such as food and live animals, beverages, and tobacco. The expanding field of influence (214.373 to 268.898) and the ratio of impacts to Ghana's GDP (0.058% to 0.062%, then 0.044%) substantiate their pronounced role in the economy. The ARDL model showed that a percent increase in Ghana-Nigeria exports led to a 0.1017% increase in Ghana's real GDP on the log-run. The speed of adjustment was 42.18% in each period. By providing support to exporters, both countries can leverage their comparative advantages, strengthen economic ties, and foster sustained growth through increased export trade.

Olaifa, Subair and Biala (2024) empirically investigated the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth in Nigeria between 1998 and 2012 with a view to examining the possibility of a long-term relationship existing between the two and also to account for the structural changes that may have occurred with the implementation of a free trade regime in 1986. Adopting the ordinary least squares

in estimating the relationship, they find that there is a long run relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth in Nigeria. Strong evidence was also found to support structural changes that took place in 1986 with the use of free trade policy. However, export was reported to have a negative relation to growth.

Edoumiekumo and Opukri (2024) examined the contributions of international trade (proxy with export and import values) to economic growth in Nigeria measured by real gross domestic product (RGDP). Time-series data obtained for a period of 27 years was analyzed using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique, Johansen co-integration test and Granger Causality test. The results showed that positive relationship exists between the variables and there is co-integration among the variables. The Granger Causality test realized a uni-directional relationship showing that RGDP Granger cause export and import Granger cause RGDP and export. Evidence from empirical studies from other countries also reviewed.

Abughalia and Abusalem (2024) investigated the empirical analysis on the Libyan economy and its structural changes, with special reference to Libyan foreign trade during the last three decades (1986-2022). The analysis was conducted using descriptive analytical methods and statistical tools such as linear regression analysis. The study observed that the trade process between Libya and the EU has experienced some success, leading to more economic cooperation through bilateral relations, promoting the private sector to play its role in the trade process during the period of study.

Gap in Empirical Literature

Most of the reviewed empirical works did find it difficult to research on international trade investigating its effect to GDP in Nigeria precisely. The study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design which some researches from the reviewed empirical study did not apply Balance of payment, import trade which some of the researchers didn't include were considered in this study. Regression, co-integration and causality test was implemented in this study unlike other researches in the empirical review. This study covers a recent time period of 1986-2024 on like the reviewed empirical work.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopted *ex-post facto* research design. This is a kind of research in which the researcher cannot manipulate the data that is been used. Kerlinger (1970) describes the *ex-post facto* research design, which is also called causal comparative research, as a design used when the researcher intends to determine cause-effect relationship between the dependent and independent variables with a view to establishing a causal link between them, this also led to the adoption of this research design for this study.

Sources of Data

The secondary data that was employed which sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and World Bank national accounts data (2024) of various years within the period of 1986 to 2024. Annual time series data of the variables was used and they include balance of trade, import trade and gross domestic product which was sourced from World Bank national accounts data and Central Bank of Nigeria - Statistical Bulletin (various issues) and Federal office, of statistics for the period 1986 - 2024.

Model Specification

To examine the effect of international trade, on economic growth in Nigerian, economic growth (proxy by Gross domestic Product), wasserve as dependent variables while international trade (proxy by balance of trade, and Import trade) serves as independent variable respectively. Given the above considerations, we adopted Emehelu (2023) the effects of international trade on the economic growth of Nigeria model which is specified as follows:

$$Y=f(X)$$

$$Y= X_1, +X_2 + X_3$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1, +\beta_{2i} X_2, + \beta_{3i}X_3 n + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y = Dependent variable

X₁, X₂ X₃-----X_n = the explanatory or independent variables

B₁, β₂, β₃ andδ-----β_n = the coefficient of the parameter estimates or the slope

e= Error or disturbance term

t = Time

In relating this to the study;

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BOP + \beta_{2i} IMT_{t-1} + \beta_{3i} EXT_{t-1} n + \varepsilon - \quad \quad \quad -- 3.2$$

Relating to econometric form and the variables log linearized, it will appear thus;

$$LGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LBOP + \beta_{2i} LIMT_{t-1} + \beta_{3i} LEXT_{t-1} n + \varepsilon --- 3.3$$

Where:

LBOP = Balance of payment

LIMT = Import trade

LGDP = Gross domestic product

LEXT = Export trade

β₀ = Intercept

β₁- β₃ = short-run dynamic Coefficients of the model’s adjustment long-run equilibrium

ε = error term.

A priori expectation: It is expected that β₁ – β₃> 0

Test of Hypothesis One

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BOP + \beta_{2i} IMT + \beta_{3i} EXT + n + \varepsilon - \quad \quad \quad -- 3.4$$

Relating to econometric form and the variables log linearized, it will appear thus;

$$LGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LBOP + \beta_{2i} LIMT + \beta_{3i} LEXT + n + \varepsilon --- 3.5$$

Where:

LBOP = Balance of payment

LIMT = Import trade

LGDP = Gross domestic product

LEXT = Export trade

β₀ = Intercept

β₁- β₃ = short-run dynamic Coefficients of the model’s adjustment long-run equilibrium

Decision Rule

The decision rule is based on a 5% probability value and is stated as follows:

$$H_0: \theta = \theta_0 \text{ versus } H_a: \theta \neq \theta_0$$

Test of Hypothesis Two

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IMT + \beta_2 BOP + \beta_3 EXT + n + \varepsilon \quad \text{--- 3.6}$$

Relating to econometric form and the variables log linearized, it will appear thus;

$$LGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LIMT + \beta_2 LBOP + \beta_3 LEXT + n + \varepsilon \quad \text{--- 3.7}$$

Where:

LBOP = Balance of payment

LIMT = Import trade

LGDP = Gross domestic product

LEXT = Export trade

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = short-run dynamic Coefficients of the model's adjustment long-run equilibrium

Decision Rule

The decision rule is based on a 5% probability value and is stated as follows:

$$H_0: \theta = \theta_0 \text{ versus } H_a: \theta \neq \theta_0$$

Methods of Data Analysis

Regression Analysis

Data collected was presented descriptively with aids of table, and also linear regression was used in testing the various hypothesis stated. Regression analysis was concerned with the study of the dependence of one variable (the dependent variable) on one or more other variables (the independent variables) with a view to estimating and predicting the population mean or average value of the latter (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). Linear regression helped to determine the impact of independent variable(s) on the dependent variable and to what extent. That was to determine both the direction and magnitude of the relationships, Ordinary least square (OLS) was used in testing the two hypotheses formulated.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LGDP	LIMT	LBOP	LEXT
Mean	4.764611	13.70677	13.09531	14.18041
Median	4.431222	14.17553	13.64956	14.46075
Maximum	6.303864	16.41413	15.57726	16.74443
Minimum	3.323236	8.696778	7.985144	9.096118
Std. Dev.	0.970519	2.233852	2.281732	2.237158
Skewness	0.274907	-0.652753	-0.596167	-0.672182
Kurtosis	1.486706	2.306827	2.097233	2.266935
Jarque-Bera	3.240441	2.731043	2.795813	2.930871
Probability	0.197855	0.255248	0.247114	0.230977
Sum	142.9383	411.2032	392.8593	425.4122
Sum Sq. Dev.	27.31532	144.7128	150.9828	145.1414
Observations	32	32	32	32

Source: E-views 9 output, 2024

Descriptive statistics in Table 1 shows that Gross domestic product (GDP) attained a mean of 4.764611 between 1986 and 2024 having a highest level at 6.303864 and lowest at 3.323236. Import trade (LIMT) stood on a mean of 13.70677 at a maximum 16.41413 and minimum of 8.696778 over the period. Export trade (LEXT) attained a mean of 14.18041 having a Maximum of 16.74443 and a Minimum of 9.096118, the mean of Balance of payment (LBOP) stood at 13.09531 at a maximum of 15.57726 and minimum of 7.985144. We observed from the results that our variables, is normally distributed ($p > 0.05$) and is statistically different from zero. The normality in the variable description are based on the skeweness of the variables, all the variables are negatively skewed, ($S < 0$) except GDP which was positively skewed.

Unit Root Test

It is not econometrically appropriate to carry out a regression analysis on time series data that are not stationary. Such operation is likely to produce a spurious regression result. In order to address the problem, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test was employed to determine the stationarity of the data as shown in Table 4.3

Table 2 Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF-Stat	5% critical value	P-value	Inference
LGDP	-4.721602	-2.951125	0.0006	I(1)
LEXT	-3.210706	-2.948404	0.0277	I(0)
LIMT	-3.368667	-2.951125	0.0193	I(0)
LBOP	-4.352045	-3.004861	0.0027	I(1)

Source: Author’s compilation 2024

The result of the unit root test in table 2 reveals the presence of stationarity at 5% critical level. Moreover, all our variables are not integrated of the same order. In other words, while the dependent variables LGDP attained stationarity at first difference I(1), LIMT and LEXT attained stationality at level 1(0) while BOP attained stationality at first difference I(1). In both instances, it is apparent that the calculated ADF value more negative than critical values for all the variables tested, which confirms that our series has no unit root. Moreover, to confirm the reliability of this result, the p-value of the calculated ADF values for each of the variables is less than 5% level of significance. Given that the variables integration in the same order, we are guided to check for co-integration using ARDL Bounds Text in other to determine if the variables have a short-run or long–run relationship.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Hypothesis one is restated in null and alternate form thus:

H₀₁ Balance of payments has no positive and significant effect on the Gross domestic product of Nigeria.

H₁₁ Balance of payments has positive and significant effect on the Gross domestic product of Nigeria.

Table 3: ARDL regression Model Estimation Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
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LGDP (-1)	0.918691	0.052961	17.34640	0.0000
LBOP	-0.408758	0.239342	-1.707840	0.1011
LIMIT	-0.797357	0.404744	-1.970029	0.0610
LIMIT (-1)	-0.120786	0.078480	-1.539065	0.1374
LEXT	1.395417	0.632393	2.206568	0.0376
C	-1.434891	0.478155	-3.000891	0.0064

R-squared	0.984143	Mean dependent var	4.790843
Adjusted R-squared	0.980695	S.D. dependent var	0.976814
S.E. of regression	0.135720	Akaike info criterion	-0.974460
Sum squared resid	0.423655	Schwarz criterion	-0.691572
Log likelihood	20.12968	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.885863
F-statistic	285.4861	Durbin-Watson stat	2.785358
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

$$D(LNGDP) = -0.408758172434 * D(LBOT) - 0.797356890175 * D(LIMIT) + 1.395417465425 * D(LEXT) - 0.081308865814 * (LNGDP - (-5.02722758 * LBOT (-1) - 11.29204205 * LIMIT (-1) + 17.16193494 * LEXT (-1) - 17.64740705))$$

Source: E-view 9 output, 2024

Based on table 3 above, the coefficient of the constant is -1.434891. It implies that when the independent variables are held constant, the value of the Gross domestic product (GDP) will be -1.434891. It can be observed that LBOP has negative and no significant effect on Nigeria’s GDP. This was explained by the negative coefficient value (-0.408758) of LBOP and its corresponding probability value (0.1011), which is greater than 0.05 significant levels.

From the model above, R², which is the coefficient of determination, is 0.984143. This entails that 0.98% of LBOT was explained by changes in the GDP. The adjusted R² take account of more number of regressors included in our model. The F-value (285.4861), with a probability value 0.000000 < 0.05 is an indicative that the overall regression is significant. The Durbin Watson statistics (DW) approximate value of 2.785358 which is greater than the R² shows signs of no serial auto-correlation.

Decision

The coefficient of LBOP is negative signed with p-value 0.4782 > 0.05. Thus, we reject the alternate hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis that Balance of payment has no significant impact on GDP of Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis one is restated in null and alternate form thus:

H₀₂ Import trade will have no positive and significant effect on the Gross domestic product of Nigeria.

H_{i2} Import trade will have positive and significant effect on the Gross domestic product of Nigeria.

Table 4 ARDL regression Model Estimation Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
----------	-------------	------------	-------------	--------

LGDP (-1)	0.918691	0.052961	17.34640	0.0000
LIMIT	-0.797357	0.404744	-1.970029	0.0610
LIMIT (-1)	-0.120786	0.078480	-1.539065	0.1374
LBOT	-0.408758	0.239342	-1.707840	0.1011
LEXT	1.395417	0.632393	2.206568	0.0376
C	-1.434891	0.478155	-3.000891	0.0064

R-squared	0.984143	Mean dependent var	4.790843
Adjusted R-squared	0.980695	S.D. dependent var	0.976814
S.E. of regression	0.135720	Akaike info criterion	-0.974460
Sum squared resid	0.423655	Schwarz criterion	-0.691572
Log likelihood	20.12968	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.885863
F-statistic	285.4861	Durbin-Watson stat	2.785358
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

$$LGDP = 0.918691134186 * LGDP (-1) - 0.797356890177 * LIMIT - 0.120786241908 * LIMIT (-1) - 0.408758172435 * LBOT + 1.39541746543 * LEXT - 1.43489065144$$

Source: E-view 9 output, 2024

Based on table 4 above, the coefficient of the constant is -1.434891. It implies that when the independent variables are held constant, the value of the Gross domestic product (GDP) will be -1.434891. It can be observed that LIMIT has negative and no significant effect on Nigeria's GDP. This was explained by the negative coefficient value (-0.797357) of LIMIT and its corresponding probability value (0.0610), which is greater than 0.05 significant levels. From the model above, R², which is the coefficient of determination, is 0.984143. This entails that 0.98% of LIMIT was explained by changes in the GDP. The adjusted R² take account of more number of regressors included in our model. The F-value (285.4861), with a probability value 0.000000 < 0.05 is an indicative that the overall regression is significant. The Durbin Watson statistics (DW) approximate value of 2.785358 which is greater than the R² shows signs of no serial auto-correlation.

Summary of the Findings

The following are the findings of this study:

- 1) Balance of payment has negative but no significant effect on Nigeria's Gross domestic product of Nigeria.
- 2) Import trade has negative but no significant effect on Nigeria's Gross domestic product of Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research work, it is recommended that

1. Manufacturing industries should improve on their production so that their output would be competitive in the global market. Excise duties should be lowered so as to encourage local industries so as to draw foreign investors to Nigeria.
2. It is necessary that conscious efforts should be made by government to fine-tune the various macroeconomic variables in order to provide an enabling environment to stimulate foreign trade by engaging in more in production so as to reduce importation.

Contribution to knowledge

This research has contributed to knowledge in various ways.

1. The study has contributed to knowledge by providing vital information on international trade and economic growth to guide our leaders in government in decision making and also to future researchers in their study of agricultural sector in Nigeria.
2. The study employed modified version of Emehelu(2024) and other researched reviewed in the study model in analysis of the Nigerian situation.
3. Finally, this study has provided new study evidence and also added to the enrichment of literature as regards the analysis on the impact of international trade and globalization on Nigeria economic growth both in the pre and deregulated era.

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